

Though Ti^{IV} is hydrolysed in dilute acidic solution yet hydrolysis is not anticipated at an acidity of $\geq 4.0 M$. The extraction of Ti^{IV} below $4.0 M$ hydrochloric acid concentration was found to be poor presumably due to the presence of several inextractable hydrolysed Ti^{IV} species. On increasing the hydrochloric acid concentration above $4.0 M$, the extraction coefficient increased sharply and 97.5% extraction of Ti^{IV} was registered at $6.0 M$ HCl. The $[Ti^{IV}] : [SCN]^-$ molar ratio in the organic phase corresponds to $Ti(SCN)_4$ in each set of the experiment with 4.0 to $\geq 6.0 M$ HCl acidity in the aqueous phase.

In order to determine the solvation number of the extracted species, solutions of TAP of varying concentration in carbon tetrachloride were used to extract Ti^{IV} at $6.0 M$ HCl (Table 1). A plot of log (distribution coefficient) vs log TAP gave a straight line with a slope of 1.99, indicating thereby that two molecules of TAP were associated with the extracted species.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF TAP CONCENTRATION ON THE EXTRACTION OF Ti^{IV} FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION $6.0 M$ IN HCl

$[Ti^{IV}] = 1.2 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[SCN]^- = 1.8 M$
Vol. of aq. layer = vol. of org. layer = 10 ml

TAP %	$[Ti^{IV}]_{aq} \times 10^{-3} M$	$[Ti^{IV}]_{org} \times 10^{-3} M$	D	E
2.0	101.1	186.9	1.85	64.99
5.0	77.6	210.4	2.70	73.03
12.0	22.6	265.4	11.76	92.16
15.0	19.7	268.3	13.65	93.17
17.0	17.5	270.5	15.42	93.91
20.0	14.4	273.6	19.00	95.00
22.0	13.1	274.9	21.05	95.46
25.0	9.5	278.5	29.15	96.68
30.0	8.2	279.8	34.42	97.18
33.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50
35.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50
40.0	7.1	280.9	39.15	97.50

$$D = [Ti^{IV}]_{org} / [Ti^{IV}]_{aq}, E = 100 D / (D + 1).$$

Separation of Ti^{IV} from Zr^{IV} solutions: A solution containing equivalent amounts of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} in $6.0 M$ HCl was extracted with 33% TAP solution in a 1:1 mixture of CCl_4 and hexanol. It was observed that 96.5% of Zr^{IV} was left in the aqueous phase while 85% of the Ti^{IV} was extracted into the organic layer in a single operation.

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Aromatic Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction between 1-Fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene and *p*-Substituted-aniline—A Kinetic Approach

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KINETICS of the reaction between 1-halo-2,4-dinitrobenzene and aromatic amines have been carried out through volumetric, potentiometric and spectrophotometric techniques¹⁻⁴. Since one of the products formed in the title reaction is a strong electrolyte, an attempt was made to study the kinetics of the above reaction conductometrically at three different temperatures in acetonitrile and the second order rate constant was evaluated. An attempt was also made to correlate the effect of the substituents in the *para*-position of the nucleophile through Hammett equation. Nature of the products obtained was confirmed by ir, nmr and uv spectra. From nmr spectral data, orientation of rings during substitution was evaluated.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in acetonitrile. 1-Fluoro-2,4-dinitrobenzene was re-purified by crystallisation from ether to constant melting point (26°). Aniline was purified by steam distillation, the fraction distilling between 180 and 184° was collected. *p*-Chloroaniline and *p*-bromoaniline were prepared following standard procedures⁵. Commercial samples of *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine were purified by recrystallisation to constant melting point.

The reaction was followed conductometrically in a bottle type conductivity cell kept in a thermostat ($\pm 0.015^\circ$). The conductance was recorded using a Pico conductivity bridge at appropriate regular intervals of time. The infinite reading was taken after 48 h.

Results and Discussion

The values of rate constants at different temperatures and activation parameters are reported in Table 1. The rate of the reaction was found to

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS, ENTHALPY AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION FOR THE REACTION BETWEEN 1-FLUORO-2,4-DINITROBENZENE AND *para*-SUBSTITUTED-ANILINES

[Substrate] = 0.2 M, [Nucleophile] = 0.4 M, Solvent = Acetonitrile

Compd. no.	Substi- tuent	$k (\times 10^4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger		
		318 K	328 K	338 K	k J mol ⁻¹	JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
1	None	7.67	11.22	15.61	28.94	-214
2	<i>p</i> -Cl	2.54	4.29	6.79	41.3	-184
3	<i>p</i> -Br	3.71	6.02	8.95	36.7	-195
4	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	15.69	22.6	31.95	29.1	-208
5	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	30.81	52.94	81.35	40.7	-165

* Calculated using Eyring equation.

increase with rise in temperature. For all the reactions studied, the values of ΔS^\ddagger was found to be negative indicating that the transition state is more organised than the reactants.

At each of the temperatures studied the effect of the substituent in the nucleophile on the second order rate coefficient follows the sequence, *p*-OCH₃ > *p*-CH₃ > *p*-H > *p*-Br > *p*-Cl. This is due to the inductive effect of the substituents. An electron-releasing group increases the electron density at the nucleophilic center resulting in the increase of the rate of the reaction and an electron-withdrawing group decreases the rate of the reaction.

The value of $\log(k/k_0)$ was plotted as a function of σ , the substituent constant, for the three temperatures at which the reaction was carried out. The Hammett plots are straight lines and the reaction constant ρ was calculated from the slope as -1.9215, -1.8950 and -1.8659 for the temperatures 318, 328 and 338 K, respectively. The value of ρ was found to be large and negative. The relatively large magnitude of ρ in the present study suggests the development of substantial positive charge at the reaction site during the formation of the transition state.

Product analysis: The substitution products were purified by repeated crystallisation from chloroform. Purity of the samples was tested by thin layer chromatography and also from melting point determination. Qualitative tests were performed to confirm that the substitution has occurred. Uv, ir and nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded and the nature of the substitution products was confirmed. The spectral data were assigned following standard procedures⁶⁻⁹. The N-H stretching frequency occurs in the region 3300-3250 cm⁻¹ for all the products.

The chemical shifts for the various protons present in the substitution product were analysed. The theoretically calculated values and the spectral values are in good agreement for all the protons except the H(6). The peak for this proton appears at 7.16-7.53 instead of 8.27. This is due to

anisotropic shielding effect operated in that proton H(6). Hence, it is presumed that the two benzene rings in the substitution product must be having the following spatial orientation

- 1; R = H
- 2; R = Cl
- 3; R = Br
- 4; R = CH₃
- 5; R = OCH₃

Mechanism: On the basis of the kinetic data and experimental observations, it was found that the reaction between 1-fluoro-2,4 dinitrobenzene and *para*-substituted-anilines follows second order kinetics. The reaction takes place through the formation of intermediate complex. The activation parameters and the Hammett ρ values determined for the above reaction are in favour of S_N_Ar mechanism. The reaction is presumed to take place as given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Since the reaction is base-catalysed, the decomposition of the intermediate is the rate determining step, and the rate constant for the above reaction is given by

$$k = (k_a + k_b [\text{ArNH}_2]) \frac{k_{-1}}{k_{-1}}$$

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Effect of Uv Radiation on DNA and Nucleohistone— A Preliminary Study†

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THE effect of uv radiation on nucleohistone (DNH) is important as it is a constituent of chromosome. The constituent moieties of nucleohistone that are sensitive to uv radiation are thymine¹, cytosine² and DNA³. Deoxyribose is not expected to undergo any significant photochemical reactions at the experimental wavelength (*i.e.* 254 nm)⁴. The purpose of this study is to find the difference in the degree of denaturation between DNA and nucleohistone and any reason for the same.

Experimental

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) (Lot No. D 1501) and nucleohistone (DNH) (Lot No. 4943) obtained from Sigma and Calbiochem, respectively, were dissolved in ECA (10^{-3} M EDTA, 10^{-3} M sodium cacodylate, pH 8.0) at a concentration of 30 μ g ml⁻¹. The native compounds as obtained do not get denatured on standing if cacodylic acid is present in the solution⁵. The solutions were kept in petri dishes of surface area 12.25 cm², the solution thickness being 0.82 cm. The temperature of irradiation was kept at a reported⁶ value of about 4° and there was no notable change of temperature

due to uv irradiation. The exposure dose at a fixed distance of 11.18 cm was 900×10^8 erg mm⁻².

The uv lamp (Arthur Thomas, U.K.) used emitted characteristic radiation of λ_{max} 254 and 365 nm; in the present study 254 nm radiation was used. Arrangements for variation of exposure dose, swirling of solution during irradiation, avoidance of back scattered radiation and ordinary light were made.

Results and Discussion

From Fig. 1 it is evident that the absorption maximum is at 258 nm for unirradiated DNA. The optical absorbance values, with standard deviations for unirradiated DNA at 230, 240, 250 and 260 nm are 0.180 ± 0.02 , 0.230 ± 0.01 , 0.335 ± 0.02 and 0.370 ± 0.02 , respectively. That for irradiated DNA at these wavelengths are respectively 0.235 ± 0.01 , 0.320 ± 0.01 , 0.485 ± 0.02 and 0.550 ± 0.01 . The average absorbance for these wavelengths for unirradiated DNA is 0.39. The average percentage hyperchromicity is 31.37%. It signifies that denaturation of the biopolymer has taken place. The structure is disorganised by uv radiation before there is any extensive photochemical degradation of the bases⁷. As the irradiation has not been done in a nitrogen atmosphere, the possibility of main chain scission in the DNA molecule in presence of oxygen can not be ruled out⁸. The chromophoric groups responsible for absorption in the uv spectral range studied are available more in solution when main chain scission takes place. Hence, the hyperchromicity is obtained at all the wavelengths.

Fig. 1. Uv absorption spectra of unirradiated and uv irradiated DNA; concn. of DNA = 30 μ g ml⁻¹, dose of uv irradiation = 900 erg mm⁻²: (O) unirradiated DNA, and (●) uv irradiated DNA.

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